

The Impact of Transfer Medium on Implantation and Live Birth Rates in Frozen-Thawed Embryo Transfer Cycles

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Abstract

Background: Embryo Glue, a hyaluronan-enriched transfer medium, enhances implantation rates by improving uterine receptivity. Advanced maternal age negatively impacts implantation rates in assisted reproductive technology, as implantation success declines with increasing age. The current study aimed to assess whether using Embryo Glue for embryo transfer improves implantation rates and live birth outcomes in freeze-thaw cycles.

Methods: This study involved patients undergoing ICSI-FET (Day 5) with conditions like POR, Advanced Maternal Age, RIF, PCOS, or Unexplained Infertility. After informed consent, Overall, 196 patients for this study were identified with the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Patients treated with FET using embryo glue as transfer medium were grouped as Test (n=104) while those treated with FET with standard transfer medium were grouped as Control group (n= 92) divided. Pregnancy was confirmed by measuring beta-human chorionic gonadotropin (beta-hCG) level after 14 days of embryo transfer.

Results: The test group (embryo glue) showed significantly higher implantation (25% vs. 19.6%, $p = 0.02$) and live birth rates (79.8% vs. 65.21%, $p = 0.03$) compared to the control group, attributed to the adhesive properties of the glue. Pregnancy rates were higher (52.88% vs. 45.65%) and abortion rates lower (20.19% vs. 34.78%) in the test group, demonstrating no increased miscarriage risk. Additionally, the multiple pregnancy rate was significantly higher in the test group (27.88% vs. 18.47%, $p = 0.019$), supporting the role of embryo glue in improving implantation outcomes.

Conclusion: Hyaluronan-enriched transfer medium (HETM), or embryo glue, is safe during ART. It considerably increases pregnancy and implantation rates. To avoid multiple pregnancies, the number of implanted embryos can be reduced. The positive outcomes shown for HETM are significantly outlined in this study, especially in females above 35 years old.

Keywords: Embryo Glue, Implantation, Embryo Transfer Cycles

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Introduction

ART has revolutionized the treatment option for infertility and has been instrumental in creating happiness for so many childless families. IVF and ET are the most favoured methods as far as technological improvements have raised pregnancy rates notably [1, 2]. Thus, ART outcomes depend on the patient's age, weight, endometrial receptivity, embryo quality and development, culture systems, personnel skills as well as the techniques and media used during ET. When these variables are managed well during the IVF cycle, they boost success rates, and if not managed well, result in implantation failure [3]. Another reason for failure is the inapt adhesion of the endometrial gel-like lining to the transferred embryo. Also, advanced maternal age (≥ 35 years) significantly decreases the reproductive potential as a result of a decreased oocyte reserve and quality, higher risk of embryo aneuploidy, lower fertilization rates, and poor uterine environment,

which is detrimental to implantation rate and pregnancy outcomes.

There are micro-and macromolecules in the female reproductive tract and the majority are albumin to facilitate implantation and fetal growth. In the same manner, hyaluronan in a much higher concentration forms a sticky matrix in the uterus helping to advise embryo anchoring to the endometrium [4, 5]. Those improvements made the prognosis of in vitro culture systems better in current years. Conventionally, embryo culture and transfer media are liquid, and additives include proteins such as HSA. Though they are less viscous than endometrial fluids of the natural reproductive tract, the degree of viscosity is necessary for efficient embryo attachment. Underlying structural elements, including collagen and hyaluronan, are bound with cell surface receptors such as CD44 in preimplantation embryos as well as the endometrium to foster embryological

development and implantation as well as the embryo's adhesion to the endometrium [6, 7]. It also has properties that make it easy to transfer embryos within the female reproductive tract and minimize displacement of the embryos after transfer. The product offers a better albumin-to-hyaluronan ratio and offers an ideal environment for the embryo to implant itself into the uterine wall. This paper assesses the ability of Embryo Glue to enhance implantation, pregnancy, and live birth rates in FET cycles as the transfer medium.

Material and Methods

This prospective study was conducted in the Department of ART. Institutional Ethical approval was obtained for the study. Written consent was obtained from all the participants of the study after explaining the nature of the study and possible outcomes in the vernacular language.

Inclusion Criteria

This study included patients undergoing Intracytoplasmic Sperm Injection–Frozen Embryo Transfer (ICSI-FET) on Day 5. Participants with conditions such as poor ovarian reserve (POR), RIF, polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), or unexplained infertility were eligible. Informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients undergoing ICSI with fresh embryo transfer (ET), conventional IVF, male patients with azoospermia, or those who had surgical sperm retrieval procedures were excluded from the study.

The stimulation protocol involved downregulation using a GnRH antagonist based on factors such as patient age, body mass index (BMI), and prior responses, if any. Recombinant FSH was administered for 10–12 days until the follicles reached 12–14 mm in size. Follicular development was evaluated using transvaginal sonography and blood samples to measure the E2 concentrations. At a follicular size of 18–22 mm, Human Chorionic Gonadotropin (HCG) was administered to the participants. Oocyte retrieval was performed 34–36 hours after the administration of the HCG trigger under short general anaesthesia using the ultrasound-guided transvaginal oocyte aspiration done with suction method. The follicular fluid was assessed under the stereo zoom microscope while the COCs were pre-washed in buffer media at 37°C. The oocytes were transferred to pre-equilibrated (37°C, 6% CO₂, and 5% O₂) dishes containing supplemented fertilization medium and incubated for 2–3 h. Fresh semen samples were collected via masturbation and processed using the density gradient (DG) method. Two to three hours after ovum pickup (OPU), cumulus cells were enzymatically removed using hyaluronidase (Sage

IVF Inc., 80 U/mL). Mature metaphase II (MII) oocytes were isolated and intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI) was performed using morphologically normal sperm. Post-ICSI, oocytes were incubated in a cleavage medium in a petri dish at 37°C, 6% CO₂, and 5% O₂. Fertilization was observed and scored 16–18 h after ICSI and verified by the presence of two pronuclei and two polar bodies. Embryos were cultured in cleavage medium until day 5 and then graded according to the Istanbul consensus (Grade A/1 or B/2). All Grade A and B embryos were cryopreserved on day 5 using the vitrification method.

Embryo Transfer (ET)

For FET cycle Estrogen and progesterone preparations are given for endometrial preparation until the tri-laminar stage (7–12 mm) was attained by Doppler imaging. On the transfer day, embryos were thawed by the Kitazato thawing kit and Embryos were incubated for 2 hours post-thaw to check the survival. Control group embryos were placed in G2-plus vitrolife media, whereas the test group embryos were placed in a hyaluronic acid-based medium. Day Five -grade A/B embryos were randomly transferred into the uterus using a Cook embryo transfer catheter under ultrasound guidance. The post-transfer β-hCG level was above 30 mIU/ml at 14 days after transfer is considered positive. Implantation was confirmed using ultrasound scans to identify the gestational sacs. The implantation rate was calculated as follows: [(total gestational sacs/total number of embryos transferred)] × 100. Data collected: The quantitative method was employed, and statistical software used was SPSS software and chi-square tests on outcomes, which considered the likelihood ratio test ($P < 0.05$).

Results

Overall, 196 patients for this study were identified with the inclusion and exclusion criteria criteria. Patients treated with FET using embryo glue as transfer medium were grouped as Test (n=104) while those treated with FET with standard transfer medium were grouped as Control group (n= 92). Table 1 describes the study population based on age group. Both groups, the control group using standard ET medium and the test group using Embryo Glue, had similar age distributions. The majority of patients in both groups were in the reproductive age group of 25–34 years. A significant proportion of patients in both groups were in the advanced maternal age (AMA) category (>35 years).

Table 1: Demographic profile of the patients included in the study

Age group	Standard ET medium (control) N= 92		Embryo Glue (Test) N=104	
	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Young				
25 – 28	18	19.56	20	19.23
29 – 30	30	32.60	33	31.73
31 – 34	21	22.82	23	22.11
Advanced Maternal Age (AMA)				
> 35	23	25.0	28	26.92
Total	92	100.0	104	100.0

There was also a statistically significant difference in the implantation rate between the two study groups: the test group (embryo glue) was higher than that in the control group (25% and 19.6%, $p = 0.02$) due to the adhesive nature of glue in ensuring that the embryo attaches to the endometrium. A statistically significant difference was observed in the live birth rate between the test and control groups (79.8% vs. 65.21 %, $p = 0.03$), suggesting that embryo glue as a transfer medium increases live births per IVF cycle. Furthermore, the test

group had a higher pregnancy rate (52.88% vs 45.65%) and a significantly lower abortion rate (20.19% vs 34.78%), proving that embryo glue does not increase miscarriage risk at any phase of pregnancy (Table 2). In addition, the multiple pregnancy rate was higher in the test group than in the control group (27.88% vs. 18.47%, $p = 0.019$) This confirmed our hypothesis that embryo glue enhances the implantation rate of transferred embryos.

Table 2: Comparison of various clinical parameters recorded in two groups of the study

Clinical Parameter	Embryo Glue (Test) N=104		Standard ET medium (control) N= 92		P value
	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	
Implantation Rate	26	25.0	18	19.6	0.02*
Live Birth per IVF Cycle	83	79.8	60	65.2	0.03*
Overall Pregnancy Rate	55	52.88	42	45.65	0.041*
Abortion Rate	21	20.19	32	34.78	0.02*
Multiple Pregnancy	29	27.88	17	18.47	0.019*

*Significant

The effect of Embryo Glue on the subset of patients with AMA, Table 3 presents the clinical parameters of the Embryo Glue group compared with the clinical parameters of the Standard ET medium group. However, the results showed a slightly higher clinical pregnancy rate in the Embryo Glue group than in the control group; however, this increase was not statistically significant ($p=0.067$). The implantation rate in the Embryo Glue group was significantly higher than that in the control group ($p=0.056$). Again, the multiple pregnancy rate in the Embryo Glue group was higher than that in the control group ($p = 0.02$). The cross-sectional examination of the Identified Embryo Glue group demonstrated an improved live birth rate compared to the control group by 27 ($p=0.001$).

Specifically, in the Embryo Glue group, five abortions were less than in the control group (chi-square 0.02). The higher implantation rate in the Embryo Glue group implies that the Embryo Glue may enhance the chances of embryo implantation. Higher multiple pregnancy data in the Embryo Glue group support further evaluation and possible preventative measures such as the sSET approach. The generally much higher live birth rate within the Embryo Glue group makes it potentially helpful for enhancing fertility treatment success in patients with AMAs.

Table 3: Comparison of various clinical parameters recorded in the AMA group

Clinical Parameter	Embryo Glue (Test) N=23		Standard ET medium (control) N= 28		P value
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
Clinical pregnancy	9	39.1	10	35.7	0.067
Implantation Rate	4	17.3	3	10.7	0.056
Multiple pregnancies	4	17.3	2	7.1	0.02*
Live birth	19	82.6	18	64.3	0.001*
Abortion Rate	4	17.3	9	32.1	0.02*

*Significant

A comparison of different clinical variables associated with the Young Age Group of patients in the Embryo Glue and Standard ET medium groups is shown in Table 4. The clinical pregnancy and implantation rates in the Embryo Glue group were also higher than those in the control group, but the differences were not statistically significant. The multiple pregnancy rate was significantly higher in the Embryo Glue group than in the control group, although the difference was not statistically significant. The outcome revealed that the group that underwent treatment using Embryo Glue had a

slightly lower live birth rate than the control group ($p = 0.001$). The abortion rates were again significantly lower in the Embryo Glue group than in the control group ($p=0.023$). Therefore, the lower live birth rate in the Embryo Glue group is somewhat counterintuitive and requires further investigation. Other factors related to embryo quality or patient information may have contributed to the results. The results showed that the Embryo Glue group had a significantly lower abortion rate, which may imply that the product can help maintain pregnancy.

Table 4: Comparison of various clinical parameters recorded in young group

Clinical Parameter	Embryo Glue (Test) N=69		Standard ET medium (control) N= 76		P value
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
Clinical pregnancy	40	57.9	39	51.3	0.06
Implantation Rate	19	27.5	17	22.3	0.125
Multiple pregnancies	21	30.4	16	21.0	0.228
Live birth	55	19.7	49	64.5	0.001*
Abortion Rate	14	20.3	28	36.8	0.023*

*Significant

Discussion

Implantation is a mechanism that involves complicated tissue interfaces between the early embryo and uterine endometrial tissue, which derives sustenance frequently from nutrients and hormones produced by the endometrium. Implantation failure poses a significant challenge, even with improvements in ART [8, 9]. It has been established that advanced maternal age a version impacts ART performance due to poor ovarian response during COH, low oocyte quality and number, low fertilization and implantation rates, and high miscarriage rates. Subsequently, using a mouse model, Gardner et al. [10] showed that ET medium supplemented with high hyaluronan levels affects implantation and IVF success rates. Since then, several studies have supported the hypothesis that hyaluronan does help enhance the success of embryo transfer. Thus, to use this positive effect, a commercial ET medium with a higher hyaluronan level was created and launched by Vitrolife. After Gardner's findings on hyaluronan-enriched transfer medium (HETM), Schoolcraft et al. [11] presented a study showing higher implantation rates in humans

using HETM. Hyaluronan is a glycosaminoglycan present in high concentrations in various organs of the female reproductive system, including the oviduct, uterine fluid, cervix, cumulus cells, follicular fluid, and seminal plasma. At the early stage of implantation, the hyaluronan is biosynthesized and secreted by integral plasma membrane glycosyl transferase only on the external surface of the cell membrane [12]. Its action is receptor-based, most notably through interactions with CD44 receptors, which bind during crucial physiological processes such as embryogenesis.

In our present investigation, we found higher implantation rates ($p = 0.02$), live birth rates ($p = 0.03$), overall pregnancy rates, and multiple pregnancy rates ($p = 0.041$) where Embryo Glue was used in the HETM group, not only in AMA patients but in all the subjects. Moreover, the abortion rates in the HETM group were significantly lower than those in the standard transfer medium group. A systematic review by Urman et al. [13] showed that hyaluronic acid in the transfer medium enhanced the cumulative ongoing pregnancy and implantation rates of embryos and blastocysts, especially in

AMA, poor-quality embryos, and PI patients. The clinical outcomes were further improved by the use of HETMs, as reported in another study by Valojerdi et al [14]. However, a Cochrane review cited in 2014 asserted that moderate-quality evidence also indicated that hyaluronan supplementation in ART embryos might improve the likelihood of clinical pregnancy and live birth, although this study pointed out that more prospective studies of high methodological quality are required to corroborate this information. Lane et al. [15] showed that supplementation of media with hyaluronan increased the chances of cryopreserved blastocyst survival in media containing BSA or recombinant albumin. Thus, Work Everybody noted improved developmental rights and higher blastocyst yield of oocytes in bovine culture media with synthetic oviduct fluid and hyaluronan or bovine albumin. Hyaluronan may either directly stimulate the development of the embryo or make it favorable for nutrients to access the correct location. Its receptors are also expressed in human and bovine embryos during the oocyte-to-blastocyst stage [16]. In addition, hyaluronan seems to modulate the receptive endometrium, since its concentration rises markedly on the day of implantation in mice in parallel with the proliferating stromal cells. Being an RU-extended uterine component, HA inhibits the diffusion of transfer media and enhances embryo attachment to the uterine lumen [17]. This interaction is essential in the implantation process, in that the embryo must adhere to the endometrial layer. This study confirms the beneficial role of HETM for implantation during FET cycles and for post-transfer embryonic development mediated through its action on cell adhesion, proliferation, migration, and expansion. HETM enhanced the implantation, pregnancy, live birth, and multiple pregnancy rates, but at the same time reduced the abortion rates for all categories of patients and without a negative impact on any subsequent pregnancy stages.

Conclusion

Hyaluronan-enriched transfer medium (HETM), or embryo glue, is safe during the course of ART. It considerably increases pregnancy and implantation rates. To avoid multiple pregnancies, the number of implanted embryos can be reduced. The positive outcomes shown for HETM are significantly outlined in this study, especially in females above 35 years old. Embryo glue can be used safely and advantageously and can be effectively incorporated into routine practice as an appropriate transfer medium.

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